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**DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION
OF METAL HYDRIDE MATERIALS AND TECHNOLOGIES IN SOUTH AFRICA**

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ABSTRACT

Metal hydrides (MH) offer promising solutions in several niche applications related to hydrogen storage – the most challenging problem which hinders implementation of efficient and environment-friendly hydrogen energy technologies. Additional motivation for the development and implementation of the MH materials and technologies in South Africa is in the necessity to benefitiate vast mineral resources of the country which include all the components used as raw materials for the manufacturing of main kinds of practically important MH alloys, particularly, AB₂- and AB₅-type ones. This presentation overviews research, development and innovation (RDI) activities in South Africa in the field of MH materials and related technologies. Since the first decade of 2000s, these activities are mostly carried out by the South African Institute for Advanced Materials Chemistry (SAIAMC) at the University of the Western Cape (UWC). The MH-related activities are one of the key technologies developed within Hydrogen South Africa (HySA) RDI Strategy in hydrogen and fuel cell technologies (2008–2023) coordinated by the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI). This key technology is implemented by HySA Systems Centre of Competence hosted by SAIAMC / UWC.

Keywords: metal hydrides, South Africa, hydrogen storage, hydrogen separation and purification, hydrogen compression

INTRODUCTION

In 2008, the South African Government launched a long-term (15 years) National Strategy on the development and commercialisation of hydrogen and fuel cell technologies “Hydrogen South Africa” (HySA). The implementation of HySA Strategy is managed by the Department of Science and Innovation of South Africa and performed by three Centres of Competence established at the leading South African universities and research institutions, including the System Integration and Technology Validation Centre of Competence (HySA Systems) hosted by the South African Institute for Advanced Materials Chemistry (SAIAMC) at the University of the Western Cape (UWC). One of the HySA Systems activities is development and implementation of metal hydride (MH) materials and technologies. Main motivation for these works is in the beneficiation of vast mineral resources of the country. Apart from Platinum Group Metals (PGMs) whose beneficiation is a primary goal of the HySA Strategy, South Africa is in the top-ten countries which have the highest mineral reserves of all the components (Ti, Zr, V, Ni, Mn, etc.) used as raw materials for the manufacturing of main kinds of the practically important MH alloys, particularly, AB₂- and AB₅-type ones [1].

The most promising path towards beneficiation is through the applied chemistry and engineering solutions related to metal hydride technologies for hydrogen storage and related applications. Specifically, it relates to R&D on the use of South African minerals to produce metal hydrides for hydrogen storage, its separation and purification, and thermally driven compression. National industries, such as the petrochemical sector (PetroSA), production of synthetic fuels from coal (Sasol), metallurgy of PGMs and base metals (Anglo-American, Impala), – are currently consumers and/or producers of hydrogen. As the Hydrogen economy develops, these industries will shift into commercial producers and suppliers, and power generation companies (Eskom) may also become producers and/or consumers of hydrogen. Thus, within South Africa there will be a growing demand for the potential technological outputs, including hydrogen storage systems and thermal sorption technologies utilising metal hydrides.

This presentation overviews research, development, and innovation activities in South Africa in the field of MH materials and related technologies, mainly considering the works performed at the HySA Systems Centre of Competence hosted by SAIAMC / UWC.

BACKGROUND

Applications of metal hydrides (MH) utilise a reversible interaction of a hydride-forming metal/alloy, or intermetallic compound with hydrogen (either from gas phase or electrolyte). Due to unique combination of their properties, MH found numerous applications belonging to three main groups [2,3]:

- Gas phase applications (compact hydrogen storage; thermally-driven hydrogen compression and heat management; hydrogen separation and purification; catalysis; powder metallurgy; vacuum-plasma technologies).
- Electrochemical applications (NiMH batteries; air – MH batteries and fuel cells).
- Other applications (nuclear technologies; switchable mirrors; H₂ sensors).

MH technologies is a typical application-driven niche area able to provide very efficient solutions for hydrogen handling in a particular end-use application, by the tuning of a number of parameters, including component and phase composition of the parent MH material, system layout, operating conditions, etc. For every particular case, the success requires to pass whole way from material to system, including specification of target composition of the MH material, its manufacturing in the necessary amounts, development and further manufacturing of non-standard system components on the basis of MH materials, and, further, the system as a whole.

Most of the MH applications are very important for energy storage technologies including hydrogen and fuel cell ones. Metal hydrides can become an important link between components of such systems, allowing to combine realisation of processes of compact and safe hydrogen storage and its supply, along with the utilisation of waste heat released during operation of other system components [4].

Significant past activities on the MH research in South Africa took place in 1970's at CSIR. The research outputs were focused on the thermodynamics and kinetics of metal – hydrogen systems, including investigations on magnesium hydride [5,6]. Over the next two decades, the work carried out by South African researchers in the field of metal hydrides included theoretical investigations on electronic properties of metal hydrides including the palladium – hydrogen system [7,8]. More recent publications, from the year 2000 onwards, comprise of articles on the problems associated with hydrogen embrittlement of metals [9], theoretical studies on metal – hydrogen bonding [10], and the palladium hydrogen system [11].

Launching the HySA Strategy, where MH for hydrogen storage and related applications were recognised as a key technology allocated at HySA Systems, resulted in a significant increase of the South African contribution into R&D activities in this field. A brief overview of these activities is presented below.

METAL HYDRIDE RELATED ACTIVITIES AT SAIAMC AND HYSA SYSTEMS

The R&D on MH materials and technologies carried out at SAIAMC and HySA Systems since 2007 were focused on:

- Development of poisoning-tolerant MH materials and their use in systems for hydrogen extraction and purification [12,13].
- Ti-based MH alloys: development, preparation (up to 10 kg/load) and characterisation [14,15].
- Modelling of phase equilibria in the systems of H₂ gas with hydride-forming metals and alloys [16], as well as heat-and-mass transfer in the metal hydride reactors [17].
- New highly efficient hydrogen storage nanocomposites on the basis of magnesium hydride [18,19].
- Development of metal hydride systems for gas-phase applications including hydrogen storage tanks for utility vehicles [20] and industrial-scale hydrogen compressors [21].
- Development of the integrated hydrogen energy systems utilising MH [4] including a pilot prototype of hydrogen refuelling station with integrated MH compressor [22].

Presently, HySA Systems develops and implements specific products for the local and international markets, particularly, metal hydride-based technologies for hydrogen storage and compression (HySA Key Programme KP6). The Key Programme presently includes two projects: KP6-S01 “Metal hydride-based hydrogen storage systems” and KP6-S02 “Metal hydride hydrogen compressors and their integration in hydrogen refuelling stations”. The focus is put on the MH-based technologies of hydrogen storage on-board heavy-duty utility vehicles (e.g., forklifts and underground mining vehicles), as well as development of MH hydrogen compressors and their integration in refuelling stations.

CONCLUSIONS

South Africa has a solid background in the R&D on metal hydride materials and technologies mainly motivated by a possibility to beneficiate the abundant local feedstock suitable for the manufacturing of the MH materials. The RDI

activities in the field have been intensified after launch of HySA Strategy in 2008 and are mainly carried out by HySA Systems CoC hosted by SAIAMC / UWC.

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